

IMPORTANCE, CHARACTERISTICS AND TASKS OF ONLINE TRAINING

Turdaliyev Sodiqjon Mo'minjonovich

Faculty of physics and mathematics faculty of the Department of mathematics
and informatics of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Email: tsm080185@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10361949>

Annotation: In this article it is mentioned that the relevance of distance learning, its models at higher education and the importance and significance of distance learning.

Key words: Professional development, distance learning, model, pragmatism, thematic plan, training programs, class schedule and electronic portal

The relevance of distance education development is primarily due to the fact that the country's higher education system is one of the largest in the world. This system has 700 institutes, colleges and other civic educational institutions. The system includes 6 million teaching staff, employees, students and graduate students, nearly 800 scientific institutions, experimental design bureau, and experimental production enterprises.

Every year, 600,000 citizens of the country and other countries are accepted as students. Territorially distant location of educational institutions, as well as the specificity of higher school activities, creates the need for rapid exchange of large-scale commercial, normative, administrative, educational, educational-methodical and scientific information [1, 2].

Over the past thirteen years, distance learning has become a global phenomenon of educational culture, but in its essence there is a wonderful paradox: this form of education has asserted its right to exist in reality, but it cannot define, define, express what it is [3]. There is no unanimity about the definition of this phenomenon, both among the scientists of our country and among foreign scientists.

Many consider it a form of correspondence education, while others consider it a blended form of education. A.A. Andreeva, M.V. Legan, V.I. Soldatkina and T.A. We accept the following definition of scientists such as Yatsevich: "Distance education is goal-oriented interactive interaction of teachers and students with each other and with educational tools, invariant in space and time in relation to them, carried out in a specific didactic system, is an organizational process" [6, 7].

It is known that two models are used in the higher education system: classical and pragmatic models [4, 5, 2]. The classical model is based on traditional education, which is usually aimed at mastering a large amount of knowledge, transferring it from the teacher to the student. Today, this model prevails in Russian education due to the established traditions and characteristics of national culture [2].

The second model has properties of pragmatism. It focuses on competences rather than acquiring knowledge and is person-oriented. This model is flexible according to the conditions and easily changes according to the modern needs of the society. In addition to his direct tasks, the pedagogue is not only a "single information carrier", but also an organizer, manager and administrator of a group of students.

Today, both models are in use in the education system, but the educational paradigm is gradually shifting towards person-centered, innovative education. In this case, the use of information and communication technologies in education is the main factor in the development of the modern educational system of HEIs.

The current conditions and situation of modern society require from distance education not only the introduction of information technologies, but also the renewal of educational technology, forms, methods, content and tools, for this reason, the new paradigm of education is primarily not the content part of knowledge that quickly becomes outdated and always requires updating, but puts knowledge acquisition technology. This technology implemented in foreign countries is called "E-learning". in educational institutions, the term "distance education" is used to mean such concepts.

Due to the adaptability and mobility (mobility) of the management of the educational process when using MT in higher education institutions, it is possible to control the mastering of educational material by students within the framework of the training system and increase the efficiency of the self-control system [30, 31, 34].

The main functions (tasks) of distance learning in professional development courses

- The MT system should reflect the dynamics of knowledge level and teaching statistics;
- The MT system should provide the teacher with flexible and advanced tools for creating lesson plans, didactic material, etc.;

- the function of checking-testing the knowledge of students in all subjects studied in NOCs;
- the function of independent verification of knowledge using information technologies and a virtual portal;
- MT system should support teamwork and communication of local (global) network participants;
- management function: making thematic plans, educational programs, lesson schedules, calculating the pedagogical load.

It is self-evident that today the theory and methodology of vocational education and, in particular, the organization of training of MOC students is experiencing a phase of continuous renewal and development. It is possible to understand the essence of MT and the application of didactic concepts in higher education based on the regulated system of teaching in the NOCs.

References:

1. Халиков А.А. Олий таълим муассасаларида бўлажак ўқитувчилар педагогик маҳоратини ривожлантириш. Монография. – Тошкент: Иқтисод Молия, 2015. – 435 б.
2. Mike A. Males. Kids And Guns. Common Courage Press, 2001.
3. Norman Jackson. Developing Students' Creativity through a Higher Education. Conference // The Cultivation of Creativity in University Students: International Symposium. – Macao Polytechnic Institute. November, 2013.
4. Xakimova Yo.T, Sh.Ahmadaliyev, M.Botirov Teaching form and methods of teacher training in distance education. International Journal of early Childhood Special Education. 2202-2204 b.
5. Xakimova, Y. T. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MASOFAVIY TA'LIMNI JORIY QILISH BOSQICHLAR. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(6), 1139-1142.
6. Xakimova, Y. T. (2023). MASOFAVIY TA'LIM JARAYONIDA INFOGRAFIKADAN FOYDALANISH VA UNING AFZAL TOMONLARI. Conferencea, 116-119.
7. Xakimova, YT (2023). MASOFIY TA'LIM JARAYONIDA BULUT TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH "INFORMATIKA METODIKASI" FANINI O'QITISH METODIKASI. Ochiq kirish ombori , 9 (6), 238-240.
8. Iloyovich, D. I. (2022). INFORMATION SECURITY AND CYBERSECURITY TRAINING IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM. Open Access Repository, 9(12), 14-16.

9. Iloyovich, D. I. (2022). Training on Safe Use of Information and Cybersecurity in the Higher Education System. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 15, 62-64.
10. Turdaliyev, SM, Yuldashev, AR, Djo'rayev, II, & Mamadaliyev, TV (2021). Axborot xavfsizligini biznes uchun strategik qilish. ACADEMICIA: Xalqaro multidisipliner tadqiqot jurnali , 11 (4), 1019-1021.
11. Iloyovich, DI (2022). Oliy ta'lim tizimida axborotdan xavfsiz foydalanish va kiberxavfsizlik bo'yicha trening. Texas muhandislik va texnologiya jurnali , 15 , 62-64.
12. Ilyasovich, D. I. (2023). BLENDER PROGRAM AND ITS CAPABILITIES. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 41, 382-385.
13. Ilyosovich, D. I. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(5), 114-116.
14. Hakimova, Y. T. (2023). MASOFAVIY TA'LIM JARAYONIDA INFOGRAFIKADAN FOYDALANISH VA UNING AFZAL TOMONLARI. Conferencea, 116-119.
15. Hakimova, Y. T. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MASOFAVIY TA'LIMNI JORIY QILISH BOSQICHLAR. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(6), 1139-1142.
16. Hakimova Yo.T, Sh.Ahmadaliyev, M.Botirov Teaching form and methods of teacher training in distance education. International Journal of early Childhood Special Education. 2202-2204 b.
17. Hakimova, Y. T. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MASOFAVIY TA'LIMNI JORIY QILISH BOSQICHLAR. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(6), 1139-1142.
18. Iloyovich, D. I. (2022). INFORMATION SECURITY AND CYBERSECURITY TRAINING IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM. Open Access Repository, 9(12), 14-16.
19. Hakimova, Y. T., Djurayev, I. I., & Mamadjonova, S. V. (2021). INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION IN PRESCHOOL INSTITUTIONS METHODOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF INTRODUCTION OF SCIENCE "TECHNOLOGY". Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(3), 105-110.
20. Мамаджанова, С. В., Джураев, И. И., & Ботиров, М. М. (2020). Технология веб-квест на уроках информатики. Теория и практика современной науки, (6 (60)), 213-220.

21. Muydinjonov, D., Muydinjonov, Z., & Djurayev, I. (2023). SUN'IY INTELLEKT TIZIMINI INSON TAFAKKURIDAN FARQI VA TARIXI: ASOSIY SANALAR VA NOMLAR. Interpretation and researches, 1(1).
22. Мамаджанова, С. (2020). ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ДОМАШНЕЙ РАБОТЫ ПО ИНФОРМАТИКЕ, НА ОСНОВЕ МОБИЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ. Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 1(1), 6-6.
23. Iloyovich, DI (2022). Oliy ta'lim tizimida axborotdan xavfsiz foydalanish va kiberxavfsizlik bo'yicha trening. Texas muhandislik va texnologiya jurnali , 15 , 62-64.
24. Ilyosovich, D. I. (2022). USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 156-161.
25. Muydinjonov, D., Muydinjonov, Z., & Djurayev, I. (2023). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING MANUALS AND THE BASIC CONCEPTS RELATED TO IT. Interpretation and researches, 1(1).
26. Ilyosovich, DI (2022). MOBIL ILOVALAR ORQALI O'ZI-O'ZINI TA'LIM. XALQARO TADQIQAT, IT, MUHENDISLIK VA IJTIMOY FANLAR JURNALI ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876 , 16 (5), 109-113.
27. Djo'Rayev, I., Mamadaliyev, T., & Mamadaliyeva, E. (2021). ANDROID MOBIL OPERATSION TIZIMI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(3), 99-104.
28. Устаджалилова, Х. А., & Джураев, И. (2015). Учебная деятельность как ведущая в процессе обучения и воспитания здорового поколения в академическом лицее. In Теория и практика современных гуманитарных и естественных наук (pp. 58-60).
29. Hakimova, YT (2023). MASOFIY TA'LIM JARAYONIDA BULUT TECHNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH "INFORMATIKA METODIKASI" FANINI O'QITISH METODIKASI. Ochiq kirish ombori , 9 (6), 238-240.
30. Marasulova, Z. A., Akhmedova, Z. S., & Turdaliyev, S. M. (2021). Continuity and succession in teaching computer science and information technology in secondary and higher education. International Journal for Innovative Engineering and Management Research, 10(3), 201-204.
31. Akhmedova, Z., & Turdaliyev, S. M. (2022). ORGANIZATION OF COMPUTER SCIENCE BASED ON MODULE TECHNOLOGY. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(11), 671-675.

32. Akhmedova, Z., & Turdaliyev, S. (2022). THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE CREATION OF ELECTRONIC INTERACTIVE EDUCATIONAL AND PROGRAMMING IN THE TOPIC" COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY". Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 1047-1050.
33. Sodiqjon, T. (2023). AR (AUGEMENT REALITY) AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 41, 394-396.
34. Mo'minjonovič, T. S. (2023). UNITY 3D GAMING SOFTWARE AND ITS CAPABILITIES. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 41, 397-399.